

SPADE: A paradigm for a multi-purpose cyber-physical agri-drones ecosystem

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Abstract

The strategic objective of SPADE is the development of an intelligent ecosystem that addresses the “multiple purposes concept” in the light of deploying UAVs to promote sustainable digital services for the benefit of various end users in the sectors of agriculture, forestry, and livestock. This includes individual UAV usability, UAV type applicability (e.g., swarm, collaborative, autonomous, tethered), UAV governance models availability and trustworthiness. The multi-purpose character is further determined in the sensing dataspace reusability based on trained AI/Machine Learning (ML) models. These will enable sustainability and resilience of the overall life cycle of developing, setting up, offering, providing, testing, validating, refining as well as enhancing digital transformations and ‘innovation building’ services in Forestry, Cropping and Livestock Farming. The SPADE digital platform can realize the potential benefits to be reaped from the use of drones. The platform makes drone operations better accessible and controllable, as well as provides a service channel for value added services enabled by drones.

Keywords: Digital farming, Governance, Monitoring, Environment observation.

1. Introduction

With the transition of Agriculture to the digital era (Agriculture 4.0), the use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has gained popularity for undertaking a variety of applications in agriculture. Commercial applications of UAVs are mainly dedicated to operations such as aerial crop monitoring and aerial spraying (Kataridis et al., 2022; Tagarakis et al., 2022). In forestry, also, UAVs have found a wide range of applications that have mainly focused on monitoring and inventorying various aspects of the forest ecosystem and forest infrastructure with a wide variety of both drone platforms and sensors (Puliti et al., 2020). The number of potential operations in which drones can replace humans or machines increases and we are only in the infancy of this field of drone applications.

However, this perspective generates a variety of risks related to drone operations. Cyber-security breaches, physical safety, and security hazards, as well as risks of human errors are increased due to incorporation of drones (Benos et al., 2022). Also, the regulation concerning drones is still new and by and large untried over the long term, while new business ecosystems and operational processes are being elevated. Of course, the changing landscape creates many positive opportunities that can be captured to materialize drones’ potential as multi-purpose device.

2. SPADE paradigm

SPADE aims towards the development of an intelligent ecosystem addressing the “multiple purposes concept” in the light of deploying UAVs to promote sustainable digital services for the benefit of various end users in the sectors of agriculture, forestry, and livestock (Figure 1).

Figure 1. SPADE ecosystem overview.

This includes individual UAV usability, UAV type applicability (e.g., swarm, collaborative, autonomous, tethered), UAV governance models availability and trustworthiness. Multi-purpose functionality is further determined in the sensing dataspace reusability based on trained AI/Machine Learning (ML) models (Liakos et al., 2018; Benos et al. 2021). This will enable sustainability and resilience of the overall life cycle of developing, setting up, offering, providing, testing, validating, refining as well as enhancing digital transformations and ‘innovation building’ services in Forestry, Cropping and Livestock Farming. The SPADE digital platform can realize the potential benefits to be reaped from the use of drones. The platform makes drone operations better accessible and controllable, as well as provides a service channel for value added operations enabled by drones.

3. SPADE platform

SPADE advances the current state of the art in digital tools to manage agricultural and environmental data by the Digital Twin platform that completely switches the paradigm on how information is obtained and used.

The platform provides an intent-based interface for end users to require use case specific information, and the process to register, transform and provide that information is orchestrated by the platform in a transparent manner, therefore improving the user-centric nature of the technology. The SPADE platform concept is presented in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. SPADE digital twin concept.

SPADE Digital Twin framework allows for the integration of domain specific capabilities (e.g., agriculture models) and constraints (e.g., real-time aspects, privacy protection). Several high-level activities have been identified, including:

- The content intake mechanisms
- The content storage
- The normalization services
- The Digital Twin lifecycle management
- The user interfaces

Several Digital Twins are developed for the various application cases under the microservices architecture. Each significant use case subsystem in the SPADE architecture is implemented as a microservice deployed by using the most recent advances in containerization architectures, ensuring a high level of independence between the underlying infrastructure and the deployed services, and at the same time guaranteeing the horizontal scalability of the overall platform.

SPADE’s Digital Twins will capitalize the apprehension of training datasets (via UAV sensors) and the consequent rendering of ML models with quality training mechanisms under the angle of the so-called AI edge processing market.

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